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Self-realization of Protagonist in Orhan Pamuk's *The White Castle*

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Abstract: Orhan Pamuk, is a prominent contemporary Turkish novelist. As a postmodern novelist he speaks of self-identity in his novels. He is a prominent contemporary Turkish novelist. Along with many myriad international awards, he has received Nobel Prize for literature in 2006. All his novels communicate the loss of pride in his characters. This paper reflects on the inability of the protagonist to find one's own self and later on he realizes his own self with the help of other character in the novel. The plot of the novel *The White Castle* is set in historic background of Turkey. Pamuk's characters in the novel *The White Castle* are identical and the inner conflict among them is to take hold of the identity of the other characters. The character's fire quest aids to reach their destiny successfully. The characters in the process of their struggle progress to achieve knowledge and power. The present paper investigates the journey of the protagonist to discover one's identity and self.

Keywords: Identity, Inability, Conflict, Ambitious goal, Self- realization, power and knowledge.

The Insight

Everybody in their life is exposed to different problems and finally he/she takes necessary steps to solve the problem. The way in which one tackles the problem helps to realize their self. Orhan Pamuk, a postmodern novelist speaks of self-identity in his novels. He is a prominent contemporary Turkish novelist. Along with many myriad international awards, in 2006 he has received the Nobel Prize for literature (Pamuk, Orhan 1991). The novel has a preface which reveals about the origin of the text of the book. The preface says that Faruk Darvinoglu translated and created the manuscript. He asserts that he has determined the author who originally wrote the novel. He investigates the author's influence of inspiration and finds that certain information are inaccurate. The complexity of authorship begins from preface itself. The novel *The White Castle* also offers a complexity in identifying the narrator (Hoffman, 1981; Wang, 2015; Higgason, 2004).

In *The White Castle* self-realization is the prominent theme and the novel revolves around the growth of the main character Hoja. Through various experiences in their life journeys each character is able to realize themselves. The theme of journey unto the self clearly emerges through reading of the novel. Hoja is the round character in the novel *The White Castle*; he is transformed from innocence to experience in his life journey (Kohzadi & Azizmohammadi, 2013). The author introduces him in the second chapter where the Italian scholar is struck awe by Hoja's appearance as both resemble each other. The pasha introduces the Italian scholar to Hoja as a slave with a bundle of knowledge. He has acquired knowledge about science, astronomy and engineering, etc. Hoja's journey begins from the place, when he meets another person of high intelligence. He feels that still he does not have proper recognition in the sultan's court. So in order to prove himself as the best astrologer, he works hard and such ambition nurtures his self-confidence. Hoja tastes the sweet of success for the first time when a rocket flies up to an extraordinary height during a celebration. He confidently believes that one day he can launch a rocket to the moon (Hunley, 1995).

There is a strong notion of hope in the words of Hoja. Ambitious men should possess strong will power to face the obstacles in their journey. Most important thing is that there must be always a quest in their heart. The quest must be like a fire lighter so that one can reach his destiny successfully. The quest for scientific western knowledge pulls Hoja forward. He never feels despair and never worries about his personal flaws. He is very much eager and interested in gaining knowledge though the person who teaches him is an Italian slave. He wishes to learn from the slave. Hoja with great concentration quickly obtains the basic of science knowledge from the Italian scholar. At the end of six months the knowledge acquired by Hoja is equivalent to the Italian scholar's. Hoja is able to create new ideas and the scholar guides him with his known knowledge.

The journey begins from innocence to experience. Within the period of six months, Hoja equips himself with scientific knowledge. He progresses with new discoveries and he receives purse of gold from pasha for the firework display on a wedding ceremony. He tastes the first success. Afterwards he starts to read many books and he takes so much effort to create a telescope and a prayer clock. He spends hours to create the prayer clock. He intends to develop a large timepiece which requires adjustment once in a month and later he plans to invent clock that require adjustment for once in year. He finds way out to set the timepiece in a proper logical method.

Hoja is overwhelmed with joy as he could also create new apparatus. So his enthusiasm escalates to discover more and more. He wants to acclaim the favour of sultan. In due course, fortune favours him. He, with the assistance of the scholar, writes two treatises. Later he gets a chance to interpret an animal hunt event and Hoja predicts that sultan loves Hoja's bestiaries. A few days later, Sultan grants piece of land to Hoja as a gift.

Hoja and the scholar live together and share their ideas. Hoja wants to begin a game that they have to write about their past life. They sit together to write it. They know about each other's past life in two months which help Hoja later to take up the place of the Italian scholar. The conscience of Hoja starts to contemplate who he is? , what his real caliber is? He searches for his real identity. The Italian scholar advises Hoja to write about his weakness and that will help him to know about the self.

He starts to write every morning and confesses everything through his writing. This gives an opportunity to know who he is and what he is capable of. As the plague starts to spread in the city, there is a twist in the novel. Hoja with his pseudoscientific stories deceives sultan in the beginning. But with the knowledge of the scholar, Hoja is able to control the plague; he takes preventive methods to control the plague disease. Sultan uplifts Hoja to the higher position in his court. Hoja becomes the imperial astrologer.

Gradually, Hoja travels towards his goal of proving his intelligence and as a result, his scientific thirst is fulfilled when he gets approval for creating powerful weapon against their country enemies. Sultan contributes fund for designing incredible weapon against their country enemies. Hoja is ecstatic by the decision taken by the Sultan and begins the venture with great zeal.

Thus Hoja is satisfied in his journey when his ideas are taken into consideration by the court of sultan. Yet Hoja has to face obstacles and personal inabilities to reach this point. Though externally he is happy, there is an inner voice which is always groaning. He is much worried about his real self (Klee & Siddiq, 1978).

The time he meets the Italian scholar is a golden opportunity for Hoja. He learns everything from him and gains his knowledge. But with the gained knowledge he is unable to think independently. He always depends on the scholar for his every action. If this condition of mind can be treated psychologically it is the inferiority complex of Hoja which is elevated through conflict. That is, according to Freud, the conflict between id and super ego. It can be simply explained as conflict between individual and society. The society expects Hoja to be an intellectual but he is not up to the mark of expectation. So Hoja adopts the defense mechanism called 'projection' by showing himself as superior to the Italian scholar.

Alfred Adler in his psychoanalytical theory discusses the inferiority complex. He says inferiority complex is a discrepancy between self-concept and self-ideal. The self-concept is all about the sense of who one is. The self-ideal refers to the sense of how one should be? So Hoja's feeling of inferiority to the scholar is debilitating. The inferiority complex results in the projection of external impulses. Hoja treats the scholar as a slave. The scholar is able to express his previous flaws without any discomfort but for Hoja it is difficult to express his own fault, as the super ego prevents him to express his self, honestly. He blames the people who live around him and finally he torches the scholar. Hoja acts frantically by tying the scholar at the chair and starts to stare at him. He instructs the scholar to write whatever comes on Hoja's mind (Falah, 2019).

Ignorance is an important obstacle for Hoja to face. He gains information and knowledge from the scholar but he depends upon the scholar in many circumstances. He earnestly seeks help from the scholar. In many situations, whether to tell stories or to interpret the dreams or to foretell the events as astrologer in the sultan court, Hoja faces many problems. In order to maintain his power in the court, he strains his individual personality. He has less self-confidence which is another great obstacle in his life journey. At one point he couldn't think and speak in the court in order to seek the attention of Sultan. So he pleases the scholar for helping hand and says that he cannot progress without the scholar's assistance.

Hoja completely depends on the Italian scholar. Hoja unable creates his own idea and to write. He loses his self-confidence and courage. He always expects the Scholar to give opinion for Hoja's Idea. Sultan calls upon the astrologer, Hoja to foretell about the plague. Sultan enquires when the plague will end. Hoja understands that this is a great prospect that if he is able set right this Plague the sultan will respect and recognize Hoja. But Hoja is helpless he fails to predict the future as an astrologer so he frankly advanced to seek help from the Italian scholar (Richardson, 1946).

Thus Hoja's lack of self-confidence leads to fear. The fear of personal inability to fulfill the society's needs forces him to depend on the Italian scholar. The dependence on scholar's knowledge is a great blow in the life of Hoja. He couldn't evaluate his self and till the end of the failure of the weapon he couldn't analyze his self. He doesn't know what he wants really. Only his circumstances lead him to choose the path. Otherwise he would remain dependent on the scholar forever. As the weapon failed the fear of punishment drives him to take up a new life in a foreign country as an Italian. The journey of Hoja reaches its destiny after many struggles. The conflicts in the inner mind of Hoja get resolved when he takes the decision on his own at the end. The journey is both physical and mental. Hoja travels with the Italian scholar for many years. Only when a situation arises, he takes the decision and finds who he really wanted to be. The circumstances decide the life of every man. The destiny is determined by environment not by one self (Karp, 2014).

Hoja becomes Italian scholar not only because of the situation but there are a few other aspects that support to take decision. The main aspect is the appearance of the two characters. Both Hoja and the scholar look identical. Their physical resemblance helps Hoja easily to take up the position of the other person. They exchange their identities without any difficulty. As they look identical it is enough to exchange their clothes. Hoja needs to shave his beard and Italian needs grow his beard. Hoja says that the scholar is freeman and no more a slave to Sultan. On the other hand Hoja remember all details about the scholar, so he takes the identity of the scholar and going to settle in Italy.

The scholar has predicted the future and also the desire of Hoja which is hidden in the unconscious mind. The quest for knowledge leads Hoja to travel forward and he realizes his self at the end.

Another aspect for his becoming is to grow up as some other person. It is his admiration on the knowledge possessed by the scholar. It can be either influence or admiration through which Hoja finds his path to tread. When he walks, he finds what he really needs and also understands who he is. Individuality represents one character from other and the self-need not be unique. There is nothing that can be defined as unique or distinct. Everybody tends to imitate others and sometimes it acts as an inspiration for the purpose of growth.

The failure of the weapon is an important event to take a decision at the final stage. Every action has its own reason and also respective consequences. Hoja with his full effort creates a powerful weapon, by working day and night. His full concentration is on making the weapon successful. A perfect time has come, the sultan has summoned both of them and their weapons to Edirne for the campaign. They create a weapon but their attempts fail as the weapon got struck in the swampy land. Sultan has planned to capture Doppio castle which has beautiful white towers. It is in the purest white and it looks fantastic. It can be called the white castle. Hoja and the scholar could sense the failure of the war. The soldiers fail to capture the castle. A few more countries have joined together with poles and that leads to failure of sultan. Thus the sultan is defeated. At this point Hoja makes a move to a new world of life and he wants to be successful in his life. He just leaves his county and determines to take up the role of the Italian scholar. He transforms himself into some other person. He finds his self at the end.

Through the scholar Hoja gains scientific knowledge and he also utilizes his ideas to his benefit. He influences sultan in every aspect and becomes the imperial astrologer. On the other hand the scholar feels jealous of Hoja as his name and fame are extorted by the initiatives taken by the scholar. When the scholar's efforts are unrewarded he gets disgusted. When a chance comes to perform the role of the imperial astrologer, he contentedly accepts the other part of his new life and gives up his dream of going back to his country. So both the souls are happy in exchanging their path. This mutual understanding is an important aspect and turning point in the life of this identical person.

There must be fear in Hoja's mind before leaving for his country because he is going as a replica of the scholar. He must know every important incident that happened to the Italian scholar in his past. He could perfectly imitate the scholar only if he knows the details. The scholar gives adequate information which helps Hoja to travel further otherwise it will be difficult to reach his destiny successfully. The scholar gives instructions to Hoja when he leaves to Italy. The scholar instructs Hoja how to find his parents and other family members. He tells about his social status in his region where he lives. So with the support of the scholar Hoja reaches his desired land at the end. They exchange their clothes, medals and their ring.

The journey thus comes to an end and Hoja realizes his self. So far his soul throbs and reaches its destiny. Only when it takes up the shape of some other person it is thoroughly contented. Psychologically there is despair in the heart of Hoja. This feeling is evoked when he meets a person who looks exactly like him and his knowledge impresses him very much. The inner self nags and he always wanted to be like the other person. It takes many years to find his self. The super ego stands as a great hurdle for him and the desired feeling is suppressed in his mind for a long time. In the unconscious mind Hoja wants to live with good recognition. When the weapon fails, he fears about his reputation among sultan and public. He wants to escape from the situation. So therefore he changes his life style. As Lacan's says "I am where I think not" that is, in unconscious, where my true selfhood lies" (Barry 2010). At the end, the suppressed and repressed thought in the unconscious mind reveal his true self. He finds his self at the end of his journey.

This process of reaching one's self is a kind of defense mechanisms. Hoja wants to defend him from the real world and the problematic circumstances and act according to his real unconscious mind. His repressed feelings take a displacement that is to change his idea from the one he has already decided. Hoja makes a shift in his idea; he turns his attention from

becoming a great astrologer into an Italian scholar. There is a displacement in the mind of Hoja in order to avoid any unhealthy situation.

The vaulting ambition or craving mind of Hoja transforms him as another person. He craves to live like the Italian scholar and he imitates perfectly like him. This strong desire of changing oneself pulls him to take the place of the scholar and that is his ambition for a long time. Lacan says “ ‘who is this other to whom I am more attached than to myself, since at the heart of my assent to my own identity it is still he who wags me.’”(Barry 2010). In the heart of Hoja, it is the scholar who strongly inspired him by his past life experiences and that helps him to become other person, as the result he find himself.

Thus the novel *The White Castle* is a journey unto the self. There is less space for uniqueness in finding one self and the individual selfhood is deconstructed. Human nature tends to be influenced by other men. That’s how Hoja is transformed into an Italian scholar. The title *The White Castle* stands as a metaphor for self-journey. Castle is a place where some secret is hidden as in the novel finding the self of Hoja is a secret. When one tries to travel into the castle the secret is revealed as Hoja travels and lives with the scholar, he finds his self.

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